

Table S1: List of primer sequences 5'-3' used for real-time PCR analysis.

PRIMER	SEQUENCE
GAPDH fw	5'-CCC CCA ATG TAT CCG TTG TG-3'
GAPDH rev	5'-TAG CCC AGG ATG CCC TTT AGT-3'
COL1A1 fw	5'-TAAGGGTGAAGCTGGTCCCC-3'
COL1A1 rev	5'- TTCACCACTGTTGCCTTTGG-3'
COL1A2 fw	5'-CCTCAGGGTGTTCAAGGTGG-3'
COL1A2 rev	5'- GACCACGTTCTCCTCTTGG-3'
COL3A1 fw	5'- CACAGAGGCTTTGATGGACG-3'
COL3A1 rev	5'- AACCTCACCTTAGCACCAG-3'
COL4A1 fw	5'- TCCAGGTTTCGCTGTTCCA-3'
COL4A1 rev	5'- GCTCTCTCCTTTCTGACCTTTC-3'
TGFβ1 fw	5'- ACCAAGGAGACGGAATACAGG- 3'
TGFβ1 rev	5'-AGGACCTTGCTGTACTGTGT-3'
CTGF fw	5'- CCTAGCTGCCTACCGACTG- 3'
CTGF rev	5'- TTTTGCCCTTCTTAATGTTTTCC-3'
ACTA2 fw	5'- TGGAAAAGATCTGGCACCAC-3'
ACTA2 rev	5'- GAGTCCAGCACAATACCAGT- 3'